

A STUDY ON THE ATTITUDE OF SELF-FINANCE COLLEGE PROFESSORS TOWARDS TNSET WITH REFERENCE TO PUDUPALAYAM VILLAGE

Lubna Suraiya

Former Assistant Professor of Commerce, Loyola College, Vettavalam,
Thiruvannamalai, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

Government of India through its notification in 1988 stated that only those candidates would be considered eligible for the post of lecturer besides fulfilling the minimum academic qualification also qualify in a comprehensive test to be conducted for the purpose. National Eligibility Test is conducted by the National Educational Bureau of University Grants Commission on all India basis. The main objective of this exam is to determine the eligibility for lecturership to ensure minimum standards for the entrants in teaching profession and research. Similarly State Eligibility Test is conducted by the State Governments on the same pattern which makes the candidate to appear in their own language and is applicable only to particular state universities/colleges for the lecture post in Government run colleges for which state they had applied. Former it was called as SLET now modified as SET. It has become an attractive option due to high salary and social respect.

Key Words: Lecturership, Minimum Standards, National Eligibility Test, University Grants Commission and State Eligibility Test

Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To understand the concept of TNSET.
- ✓ To study the attitude of self-finance college professors towards TNSET.
- ✓ To arrive at the findings and recommend suggestions based on the study.

Statement of the Problem:

To make certain about the quality assurance in academics as well in research for which such government eligible examinations are being conducted. There is a real need to focus on the system of education in Tamil Nadu and academicians being employed in Government Colleges. However, in most cases, candidates with high academic profile or experience are considered non-eligible for the reason that they do not possess such parameters and are camouflaged or eye-washed in current scenario where the prime spotlight is open unscrupulous bribery for a candidature to crack these examinations.

Methodology:

Cronbach's Alpha is used to measure the internal consistency of the questionnaire. The researcher used interview schedule as the data collection tool using Likert Five Point Scaling. The present study is based on Simple Random Sampling method with a sample size holding 60. The area of the study is Pudupalayam Village of Chengam Taluk of Tiruvannamalai District. The research was carried out by using both primary data and secondary data. The required primary data was collected from the respondents directly. The secondary data were collected from various sources including books, periodicals, articles, research papers, newspapers, websites and manuals.

Review of Literature:

Lubna Suraiya (2018) made an attempt to obtain the views regarding the attitude of Self-Finance College Professors towards TNSET Examinations. The researcher expressed that Government is trying to elevate standards in teaching and to encourage research related activities which are highly recommended. But on the other hand, the Government of Tamil Nadu fails to maintain the key ordinance, by rooting out utmost good faith through misconduct of subornment and also demoralize the eminent caliber candidature. The handicapped Government does not prove worth in providing employment opportunities for the unemployed particularly those who are into college teaching profession and therefore plays a double edged game for the meager sake by conducting such qualified examinations to crack and be better placed in Government run colleges which is absolutely making people strenuous, ravage of money, loss of hope, indirectly tempting for corruption, availing benefits at the nearing time of retirement is the real scene and more worsened situation may arise in the years to come.

Research Gap:

Though numerous studies are made available on the system of education but no reviews are found with regard to TNSET examinations and lack quantitative means. Knowing thoroughly about the present condition to crack this examination yet academicians appear. This study helps to know the attitude of Professors of Self-

Finance Colleges. This was the research gap identified by the researcher and furthermore made the researcher to go for the study.

Limitations of the Study:

The researcher has taken all possible effort and care to avoid the statistical discrepancy and reliability of data supplied both at the time of collection of data and secondary review collection. However the present study is subjected to under mentioned limitations.

- ✓ This study is confined to Pudupalayam village only and may not be applicable to whole of Tamil Nadu State.
- ✓ Data regarding their opinions and attitudes may not be accurate as the respondents recalled from their memory and few shared their experiences that they are facing.

Application of Tools:

Percentage Analysis: Percentage Analysis is applied to create a contingency table from the frequency distribution and represent the collected data for better understanding.

Age of the Respondents: Age factor is the most important aspect. Professors of Self-finance Colleges belong to different age groups. The following table shows the age wise classification of the respondents.

Table 1.1: Age of the respondents

S.No	Age (in years)	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	18 – 25	6	10
2	26 – 34	34	56.66
3	35 – 46	16	26.67
4	Above 47	4	6.67
Total		60	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference: Table 1.1 confirmed the age of the respondents. It is evident from the above table that 34 respondents (56.66 percent) of the respondents are in the age group of 26 - 34 years, 16 respondents (26.67 percent) fall in the age group of 35 - 46 years, 6 respondents (10 percent) are in the age group of 18 - 25 years and 4 respondents (6.67 percentage) comprises the age group of above 47 years. Majority of the respondents belongs to the age group between 26 - 34 years which is primarily the most dominating age group.

Level of Education of the Respondents:

The level of education is included as one of the important profiles of the respondents as it may have its own influence on the attitude towards TNSET examinations.

Table 1.2: Educational Qualification among the Respondents

S.No	Educational Qualification	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Post Graduates	12	20.00
2	M.Phil Degree Holders	37	61.67
3	Doctorates	3	05.00
4	Professional Studies	8	13.33
Total		60	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference: Table 1.2 highlights the educational qualification of the respondents. In this study it was confirmed that 37 (61.67 percent) of the respondents have possessed M.Phil degrees. 12 (20 percent) have completed Post Graduation. 8 (13.33 percent) hold Professional Studies, 3 (5 percent) are Doctoral Degree Holders. The analysis reveals that majority of the respondents are M.Phil Degree Holders as their level of education.

Occupation of the Respondents:

The occupational background of the respondents is included as one of the profile variables that may lead to different levels of attitudinal prospects of the respondents. The distribution of the respondents on the basis of occupation is presented in the Table 1.3

Table 1.3: Occupation of the Respondents

S.No	Occupation	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Professors	2	3.33
2	Associate Professors	22	36.67
3	Assistant Professors	36	60
Total		60	100

Source: Primary Data

Inference: The important occupational background among the respondents 36 (60 percent) are Assistant Professors. Associate Professors form 22 (36.67 percent) to the total of the occupational background. 2 (3.33 percent) constitute Professors. Among the occupational background, it is Assistant Professors who comprises in majority.

Garrett Ranking Technique:

As per this method, respondents have been asked to assign the rank for all factors and the outcomes of such ranking have been converted into score value with the help of the following formula:

$$\text{Percent Position} = \frac{100 (R_{ij} - 0.5)}{N_j}$$

Where, R_{ij} = Rank given for the i^{th} variable by j^{th} respondents, N_j = Number of variable ranked by j^{th} respondents

With the help of Garrett’s Table, the percent position estimated is converted into scores. Then for each factor, the scores of each individual are added and then total value of scores and mean values of score is calculated. The factors having highest mean value is considered to be the most important factor.

Table 1.4: Calculation of Percentile Position

Variables	Percentile Position	Garrett’s Table Value
Crooked Practices	$100 (1-0.5)/8 = 6.25$	80
Utter allegiance and hard work	$100 (2-0.5)/8 = 18.25$	68
Favour of luck belief	$100 (3-0.5)/8 = 31.25$	60
Opaque information regarding cut-off allocations	$100 (4-0.5)/8 = 43.75$	53
Shortage on recruitment of qualified aspirants	$100 (5-0.5)/8 = 56.25$	47
Hike in fee structure	$100 (6-0.5)/8 = 68.75$	41
Changes in applying varying upon universities especially in uploading credentials	$100 (7-0.5)/8 = 81.25$	33
Unsystematic follow up of syllabus and discrimination during examinations	$100 (8-0.5)/8 = 93.75$	21

Source: Primary Data

Table 1.5: Attitudinal Ranking of the Respondents

Factors	Assigned Ranks								Total	Total Score	Mean Score	Rank
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8				
Crooked Practices	22	5	7	9	2	4	3	8	60	4800	80	1
Utter allegiance	7	10	13	15	6	8	1	0	60	4080	68	2
Belief in good fortune	15	6	4	6	5	8	14	2	60	3600	60	3
Opaque on cut-off marks	16	7	5	8	7	10	3	4	60	3180	53	4
Recruitment shortage of qualified aspirants	6	9	15	10	2	6	8	4	60	2820	47	5
Hike in fee structure	3	16	9	4	11	10	2	5	60	2460	41	6
Variations in applying	12	6	1	16	2	9	4	10	60	1815	30.25	7
Unsystematic follow-up	9	9	9	18	6	3	4	2	60	1260	21	8

Source: Primary Data

Findings:

- ✓ Based on the milieu of the respondents, 34 respondents (56.66 percent) of the respondents are in the age group of 26 - 34 years.
- ✓ 37 (61.67 percent) of the respondents are in majority according to their level of education possessing M.Phil Degree Holders.
- ✓ On the basis of the occupation it is found that among the respondents constitute 36 (60 percent) are Assistant Professors.
- ✓ The first rank is preferred towards involvement of crooked practices in TNSET Examinations, second rank to utter allegiances of the respondents followed by good luck, non-transparency in cut-off marks, recruitment shortage of qualified aspirants, hike in fee structure, variations in applying and the least rank is rated ultimately for unsystematic follow-up of syllabus structure and discrimination prevailing during examinations.

Suggestions:

- ✓ Government of Tamil Nadu must stabilize the regulations to be followed for TNSET Examinations irrespective of different universities being the Nodal Agency to conduct.
- ✓ Transparency in cut-off marks must be allocated prior to the examination being conducted, so as to ease the candidates in clearing this examination.
- ✓ Affordable fee structure should be taken into consideration.
- ✓ Strict Vigilance shall be observed to avoid unprofessional conduct followed if any and shall seriously be punishable or dealt with. This phase requires a greater caution to shun negligence and must be a change agent not merely by words but transforming into action.
- ✓ Examinations must be as per the accordance with the syllabus and proportionate coverage of all the subjects is necessary.

- ✓ According to their respective discipline only one Paper shall be entertained including on a common ground the set of General Aptitude.

Conclusion:

TNSET enable the candidate for a stronger preparation and helps to acquire in-depth knowledge about the curriculum. However, there is a probability to be agreed upon that not necessary that all qualified candidates may have surpassing knowledge where in most cases only a very few possess this eminence and the unqualified candidates do not meet the standard eligibility. It completely depends upon the personal interest and dedication of the candidate to reap rewards for the hard work to crack these examinations.

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